

SND metadata profile

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Version: 2

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Background

To make it easier for researchers from various fields to describe and share data, SND has developed several metadata profiles that are specific for certain fields, or topics. The goal is to offer adapted profiles for all the subjects at the broad classification level of the OECD Fields of Research and Development classification (FORD)¹. Apart from these topic-specific profiles, SND also offers a general profile to fit broader uses, which is intended to be used for resources originating from research fields that don't have a specific metadata profile.²

To date, in autumn 2023, SND supports the following metadata profiles:

- General
- Medical and Health Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD)
- Natural Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD)
- Social Sciences (broad classification in OECD FORD)
- Engineering and Technology (broad classification in OECD FORD)
- History and Archaeology
- Earth and Related Environmental Sciences
- Language Resources

There is additional profile for *entry level data*; a minimum metadata profile that fulfils the DataCite requirements to issue a DOI for a dataset. This profile is not included in SND's certification as a Trusted Seal Depository³ and can only be selected at an organization level for research principals with local data storage. Data with an entry level profile only meet the FAIR criteria to a limited degree and receive a disclaimer on their landing page in the SND research data catalogue.

Structure

SND's metadata are based on the metadata standard Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)⁴ and on recommendations from DataCite. The specific profiles also support domain-specific standards and international research infrastructures.

At the core is SND's master profile, *SND Master*, which contains all of the metadata elements, and their properties, that SND supports. The specific profiles then use the elements that are relevant to each field, as well as domain-specific key words.

¹ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/classifications/Family/Detail/1039>

² Metadata profiles for the Humanities and the Arts and for Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences are planned for development and launch in 2022.

³ SND is certified according to the Core Trust Seal, <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>.

⁴ <https://ddialliance.org/>

All profiles have some mandatory metadata elements in common; these elements are specified in the documentation for SND Master. Each respective profile can then have further mandatory elements, which will be specified in the documentation for the profile.

Documentation

The SND metadata profiles are documented separately, based on the documentation for SND Master.

Every metadata element has the following information:

ID	A unique identifier for each metadata field. The identifier is global to all profiles.
Element	The name of the metadata element, in Swedish and English.
Definition	The element definition in Swedish and English.
Allowed content	A description of which information/values are allowed for the element. For example, controlled vocabularies are written "CV: DDI".
Occurrence	The element's cardinality: 0-n = optional and repeatable 0-1 = optional, non-repeatable 1-n = mandatory and repeatable 1 = mandatory, non-repeatable
Terms	A description of whether there are specific conditions for the visibility of the element.
Comment	Further explanatory comments.

Versions

Version 1 2022-06-23	
Version 2 2023-08-28	Deleted elements: D2, D4, D5, D6, D7, D9, D17, D18 New name (English): S16.1 New definition: S16, S25 New allowed content: S32, S37.1